

xAPI Learning Record Document

Oliver Pincus
DeLT Labs GmbH

ABSTRACT

An xAPI Learning Record Document (LRD) is a PDF file that keeps a secure record of a learning activity using xAPI statements. It is designed to be both human and machine readable and is owned by the learner. The Learning Record Document enables learners and organizations to share data about learning activities using xAPI as a data standard without sending data to a Learning Record Store (LRS).

1. INTRODUCTION

The xAPI Standard (IEEE 9274.1.1, <https://opensource.ieee.org/xapi>) recommends tracking learning experiences through HTTP requests initiated by the Learning Record Provider (LRP) and directed to the Learning Record Store (LRS).

A Learning Record Documents saves one or more xAPI statements for a learning activity as JSON files attached to a PDF file.

The attached xAPI statement is signed by the issuer of the Learning Record Document using a certificate. The presence of a valid JWT token confirms that the data remains unmodified by the learner, thereby preserving its integrity and verifying its source.

The Learning Record Document is shared with the learner as a PDF file. The learner decides where to store and when to share the file.

Organizations may collect Learning Record Documents submitted by learners, extract the xAPI statements from them, and store this data in a Learning Record Store (LRS) for further analysis and reporting.

The specification for the xAPI Learning Record Document is available at <https://github.com/deltlabsdev/xapi-lrd>.

2. SPECIFICATION

The Learning Record Document is a PDF file using the PDF 1.7 (ISO 32000-1) or the PDF 2.0 (ISO 32000-2) standard that includes file attachments.

The PDF file must not be encrypted.

2.1 PDF CONTENT

There are no constraints or predefined requirements regarding the human-readable content of the PDF file. The content layout, structure, and design are fully flexible and may be implemented at the discretion of the developer or designer.

The PDF content should include the following elements:

- Issuer name (organization name)

- Activity Type (Activity, Webinar, Video, ...)
- Activity Details
- Statement ID (GUID)
- Date issued
- URL of website or API that is used to generate the Learning Record Document

2.2 PDF ATTACHMENTS

The machine-readable data of the Learning Record Document is saved in PDF file attachments. PDF file attachments are files that are embedded within a PDF document.

The file attachments should be text files (.txt, .json). In certain scenarios, media files such as images may be included as attachments. A Learning Record Document must not include any executable files as attachments.

2.3 STATEMENT.JSON ATTACHMENT

A Learning Record Document must include a statement.json file attachment.

The attachment statement.json must include a valid single xAPI statement following the IEEE Standard 9274.1.1 as string.

A Learning Record Document may use an xAPI statement with an unidentified actor.

2.4 JWT.TXT ATTACHMENT

A Learning Record Document must include a jwt.txt file attachment.

The attachment jwt.txt must contain a valid JWT token generated in compliance with RFC 7519 with the content of the statement.json attachment as payload.

The JWT header shall include the X.509 certificate chain. This is an array that contains the X.509 certificate chain, using "x5c" and a base64-encoded representation of the DER-encoded certificate. If there is a certificate chain, each certificate should be base64-encoded and included in order.

The signature is created by signing the encoded header and payload with the RSA private key corresponding to the public key in the X.509 certificate, using the RS256 algorithm.

The JWT token must be saved as string in the file attachment jwt.txt.

2.5 README.TXT ATTACHMENT

A Learning Record Document must include a readme.txt file attachment.

The readme.txt may contain any text that describes the Learning Record Document. The attachment shall contain the URL of the issuer of the Learning Record Document.

2.6 STATEMENTS.JSON ATTACHMENT

For activities that require more than one xAPI statement, a Learning Record Document may include a statements.json file attachment.

The attachment statements.json must contain a JSON list (Array) of valid xAPI statements following the IEEE Standard 9274.1.1.

2.7 JWTS.TXT ATTACHMENT

If an attachment statements.json is added to the Learning Record Document, the Learning Record Document must include an attachment jwt.txt.

The jwt.txt attachments must include a JSON list (Array) of JWT tokens for each statement saved in statements.json.

For each xAPI statement in statements.json, a JWT token must be generated in compliance with RFC 7519 with the content of the xAPI statement as payload.

The JWT header shall include the X.509 certificate chain. This is an array that contains the X.509 certificate chain, using “x5c” and a base64-encoded representation of the DER-encoded certificate. If there is a certificate chain, each certificate should be base64-encoded and included in order.

The signature is created by signing the encoded header and payload with the RSA private key corresponding to the public key in the X.509 certificate, using the RS256 algorithm.